

The Influence Of Market Attractiveness And Distinctive Capabilities On Competitiveness And The Implication On Business Performance Of Hand Loom Industry In West Java

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾ Muhammad Ade Sulchi ⁽²⁾ Dwi Kartini ⁽³⁾ Wa Ode Zusnita Muizu ⁽⁴⁾ Erie Febrian
⁽¹⁾⁽²⁾⁽³⁾⁽⁴⁾ Doctoral Program in Management Science, Faculty of Economic and Business Padjadjaran University, Bandung, Indonesia

Abstract:

The Hand Loom Industry has a big opportunity in its market, but the performance of that industry is still less optimal compared to the existing opportunities and market demands. The low business performance of the industry is allegedly caused by the competitiveness that still not high caused by the weaknesses in the ownership of distinctive capability and in adapting market attractiveness of the industry.

The objective of this study is to uncover the influence of market attractiveness and distinctive capability on competitiveness and the implication on business performance of Hand Loom Industry in West Java.

This is a causality research on the unit of analysis and observation is the company's management team of the Hand Loom Industry in West Java, which sample size of 50, that using stratified random sampling methods. Data then verified through PartialLeast Square (PLS).

The findings reveal that distinctive capability has a bigger role in enhancing competitiveness of Hand Loom Industry in West Java rather than market attractiveness. Competitiveness has a greatest influence to business performance.

Keywords: Market Attractiveness, distinctive capabilities, Business Performance

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research Background

Data from the Ministry of Cooperatives and Small and Medium Enterprises (Menkop & PKM) shows that in 2012, there were approximately 56,534,592 million small businesses with average annual sales of less than IDR 167 billion, or approximately 14.06% of the number of companies in Indonesia (reference Ministry KUKM 2013).

The industrial sector has a very important role in the economy of Indonesia, including to sustain the prosperity and growth of the Indonesian economy, besides it also being a source of foreign exchange and provide employment. This can be seen from the role or contribution of industrial sector to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) reached 59.08% and proven in some of the economic crisis, especially the small and medium enterprises of the Hand Loom Industry being a source of resilience which proved to be a balancing of the Indonesian economy. But the inherent characteristics of Hand Loom Industry can be an excess or a force that actually become an obstacle to its development (growth constraints). The combination of strengths and weaknesses and the opportunities and challenges of all of the state of the external situation will be able to determine the prospects for the development of small and medium enterprises of industrial Hand Loom it self.

The above conditions shows that business performance of Hand Loom Industry in Indonesia tend to not superior. This is presumably because the products competitiveness is not high. According to Castro et al. (2004), in order for a company considered to be competitive from the standpoint of the operative, then the company would have to design a strategy to complete the conditions : a competitive price, the products with superior quality, and high level of service to the customer (speed and variety).

However, based on the initial observations, it is known some indications that in the Hand Loom industry players, there still high operational costs of production due to the tools that are old and require more maintenance. Relatively, product design has yet its own uniqueness compared to its competitors; and variety of products on offer is still relatively limited. Moreover, in the case of services is also still has weaknesses which are still difficult to meet orders on time due to the limitations of existing tools as well as a lack of skilled experts.

Such conditions, also allegedly because management has not been able to thoroughly explore the attractiveness of the market in the area of their operations, as well as many business opportunities are still difficult to be developed, while according to Best (2013), the ability to anticipate market attractiveness can be measured through market forces, competitive intensity and market access. The industry still has

difficulties in updating technology due to the limitation of working capital and constraints in accessing markets. It is associated with the weak cooperation between companies with the trader, so that the industry players often miss the potential market both local and international market. In fact, the market opportunity is still wide both domestic and international markets.

In addition, the industry has also not been able to thoroughly develop unique capabilities. It indicated with the weaknesses in terms of ownership of tangible assets, such as working capital and the conditions of production equipment remain inadequate. It affect the handling of orders that have not been timely and yet efficiently. In addition, the ownership of intangible assets also tend to have problems, especially in terms of the creation of brand products, as well as the reputation of the company that have not been particularly good in the eyes of the market compared to the products of other countries, and then weak organizational capability, especially in creating a superior work culture. Yet Wheelen & Hunger (2012), emphasizes the empowerment of the distinctive capabilities that are superior resources. While according to Wheelen & Hunger (2012, p.138), resource is the basic building of an organization, as well as the following statement :

“Resources are an organization’s assets and are thus the basic building block of organization. They include tangible assets, such as its plant, equipment, finances, and location, human assets, in terms of the number of employees, their skill and motivation, and intangible assets, such as its technology (patents and copyrights) culture and reputation”.

1.2 Research Objective

Based on the background mentioned earlier, this study aims to examine the influence of market attractiveness and distinctive capabilities on competitiveness and the implication on business performance in the Hand Loom Industry in West Java.

1.3 Literature Review

The definition of market attractiveness based on American Marketing Association dictionary is “market attractiveness defines the degree of market opportunities provided by a market segment and a company’s ability to meet the segment’s needs considering the competitive environment” (Urbsiene, Monkeviciute, Navikate, 2014, p.117). Meanwhile, Urbsiene, Monkeviciute, Navikate (2014, p.117) concluded that “usually related to the company’s entering into a new and unknown market and closely associated with the market competitiveness”. Best (2013, p.411) argues “market attractiveness the relative attractiveness of a market based on market forces, competitive environment and market access”.

The term *capabilities* suggested by Makadok (2001:388) as follow:

“capabilities, in contrast, refer to a firm's capability to deploy resources, usually in combination, using organizational processes, to effect a desired end. They are information-based, tangible or intangible processes that are firm-specific and are developed over time through complex interactions among the firm's resources. They can abstractly be thought of as 'intermediate goods' generated by the firm to provide enhanced productivity of its resources as well as strategic flexibility and protection for its final product or service “

In the other hand, Wheelen & Hunger (2012: 138) suggest the definition below:

*“A core competency is a collection of competency that crosses divisional boundaries, is widespread within the corporation, and is something that the corporation can do exceedingly well. **Distinctive competencies** : when core competencies are superior to those of the competition. **Resources** are an organization’s assets and are thus the basic building block of organization. They include tangible assets, such as its plant, equipment, finances, and location, human assets, in terms of the number of employees, their skill and motivation, and intangible assets, such as its technology (patents and copyrights) culture and reputation. **Capabilities** refer to corporation ability to exploit its resources. A Competency is a cross-functional integration and coordination of capabilities”.*

Kim Man and Wafa (2008) stated that capabilities or distinctive competencies are the important part of resources and competitive advantage. Simonceska, (2010, p.618) suggest that “*The concept of distinctive capabilities is a process of identifying the advantages and distinctive features of the company and their exploitation in creating a specific product by which it will realize competitive on the market*”.

According to Castro et al. (2004), in order for a company considered to be competitive from the standpoint of the operative, then the company would have to design a strategy to complete the conditions : a competitive price, the products with superior quality, and high level of service to the customer (speed and variety).

Hitt, Ireland, and Hoskisson (2013, p.4) stated “*Strategic competitiveness is achieved when a firm successfully formulates and implements a value-creating strategy*”

Casadesus-Masanell & Ricart (2010, p.124) also had a definition of the term as follow :

“*a firm’s competitiveness is related to how well its business model interacts with its environment to produce offerings that add value. Three elements are important to this idea.*

First, added value means that the elimination of the firm and its offering would reduce the size of the overall “value pie.”

Second, a firm’s business model is a key determinant of its ability to add value. Adding value depends on firms having business models that can create value, and this, in turn, is a precondition for firms to be able to capture value (Brandenburger and Stuart, 1996) so as to sustain their existence.

Third, business models do not act in isolation, but rather interact with those of other industry participants – customers, suppliers, competitors, and producers of substitute and complementary products”.

In measuring business performance, Ainin et al.(2007) used *Business net profit*. Vanderstraeten and Matthyssens (2010) measure business performance by *growth*.

There are some studies show the relationship between variables. Urbsiene, Monkeviciute & Navikaite (2014) reveal that market that is not attractive had no competitiveness among other market. Pallapothu dan Evans (2013) measured market and non market forces that shaping the structure of industry are very important in determining the strategic position for every companies in the market. Sacui and Sala (2012) reveal that in the knowledge-based economic, the intangible asset is being a fundamental determined for the competitiveness of a company in the present and in the future as well as in achieving company value and growth. Maâlaoui and Nasr (2008) figure out that the competitiveness is very depend on the ability to access the knowledge needed to develop strategy and internal process efficiently. Bilalis *et al.* (2006) show that main performance indicators of the textile sector are quality management, supply chain flexibility, strategy formulation, and strategy implementation. Lau (2010) identified factor that determine business performance that is competitiveness.

Based in above description, then developed the hypothesis below :

1. Market attractiveness and distinctive capabilities influential on competitiveness.
2. Market attractiveness and distinctive capabilities influential on business performance
3. Competitiveness influential on business performance

II. METHODOLOGY

This nature of the study is causality. The unit of analysis and observation is the company’s management team of the Hand Loom Industry in West Java, which sample size of 50, that using stratified random sampling methods. The observation uses time horizon that is cross section / one shoot, meaning that information or data collected directly at a particular time. Data then verified through *Partial Least Square* (PLS).

III. DISCUSSION

Goodness of fit Model-Analysis of structural model (Inner Model)and measurement model (Inner Model)

Goodness of fit aims to examine whether the resulted model show the actual condition. This section will discuss the result of hypothesis testing by using *Partial Least Square* (PLS). The analysis of structural model (*inner model*) show the links between latent variables. Inner model is evaluated by using *Goodness of Fit Model (GoF)*, that show the difference between the values of the observations result with the values predicted by the model. This test is indicated by the value of R Square on endogenous constructs. The value of R Square is the coefficient of determination on endogenous construct. Refer to Chin (1998), the value of R square amounted to 0.67 (strong), 0.33 (medium) and 0.19 (weak). *Prediction relevance* (Q square) or known as Stone-Geisser's used to know the capability of prediction with *blinfoling* procedure. If the value obtained 0:02 (minor), 0:15 (medium) and 0:35 (large), and only used for the endogenous construct with relective indicator. Here is the value R square and Q-Square for each construct:

Table1
Test of Outer and Inner Model

Variable	R Square	Cronbachs Alpha	Composite Reliability	Q square
MARKET ATTRACTIVENESS	-	0.836	0.872	-
DISTINCTIVE CAPABILITES	-	0.917	0.930	-
COMPETITIVENESS	0.808	0.888	0.910	0.409
BUSINESS PERFORMANCE	0.872	0.852	0.755	0.420

Source: SMARTPLS v.2.00

Tabel di atas memberikan nilai R² pada kinerjabisnis sebagai variable endogen beradadalam kriteria mendekatikuat(mendekati0,6 = kuat, di atasmoderat), dannilaiQ squareberadapadakriteriabesar, sehingga dapat disimpulkan bahwa Model penelitian didukung oleh kondisi empirik atau model fit. An\\

Analysis of measurement model (*outer model*) show the link between manifest variables (indicators) with each latent variables. It is used as validity and reliability test to measure latent variabel and indicator in measuring dimension that is construct. It is can be explained by the value of *Cronbachs Alpha* that is to see the reliability of dimension in measuring variables. If the value of *Cronbachs Alpha* bigger that 0.70 (Nunnaly,1994), it show that the dimensions and indicators as reliable in measuring variables. *Composite reliability* dan *Cronbachs Alpha* of variabels > 0,70 show that all of variables in the model estimated fulfill the criteria of discriminant validity. Then, it can be concluded that all of variables has a good reliability.

Chin (2000) stated that if the *Loading factor* of measurement model is bigger that 0.50 or if the value of t of loading factor is bigger than t table on the significance of 5%, then the dimension is stated as valid in measure the variable.

Based on the research framework, then obtained a structural and measurement model as follow

a. Structural Model

$$Y = 0.473X1 + 0.537X2 + \zeta_1$$

$$Z = 0.235X1 + 0.191X2 + 0.580Y + \zeta_2$$

Dimana

Z = Business Performance

Y = Competitiveness

X1 = Market Attractiveness

X2 = Distinctive Capabilities

ζ_i = Residual

b. Measurement Model

The usage of *Second Order* in the research model cause *loading factor* obtained can explain the relationship between latent variables-dimension and dimensions-indicators. The table below show the result of measurement model for each dimensions on indicators.

Table2
Loading Factor of Dimension-Indicator

Variable	Indicator-Dimension	λ	t	Conclusion	
Market Attractiveness	X11 <- Market forces	0.718	3.709	valid	
	X12 <- Market forces	0.602	4.218	valid	
	X13 <- Market forces	0.609	3,442	valid	
	X14 <- Market forces	0.588	2.770	valid	
	X15 <- Market forces	0.744	4.162	valid	
	X21 <- Competitive intensity	0.912	18.335	valid	
	X22 <- Competitive intensity	0.833	12.661	valid	
	X23 <- Competitive intensity	0.682	4.309	valid	
	X31 <- Market access	0.857	16.062	valid	
	X32 <- Market access	0.757	3.909	valid	
	X33 <- Market access	0.746	5.168	valid	
	X34 <- Market access	0.205	2.699	valid	
	Distinctive capabilities	X41 <- tangible asset	0.674	6.375	valid
		X42 <- tangible asset	0.807	13.194	valid
X43 <- tangible asset		0.862	14.751	valid	
X44 <- tangible asset		0.745	7.735	valid	
X45 <- tangible asset		0.806	10.298	valid	
X51 <- Intangible asset		0.863	17.938	valid	
X52 <- Intangible asset		0.859	13.705	valid	
X53 <- Intangible asset		0.777	11.882	valid	
X54 <- Intangible asset		0.774	8.912	valid	
X55 <- Intangible asset		0.743	.307	valid	
X56 <- Intangible asset		0.776	9.038	valid	
X57 <- Intangible asset		0.516	2.747	valid	
Competitiveness		Y11<- Competitive price	0.941	39.563	valid
	Y12<- Competitive price	0.939	37.475	valid	
	Y21<- Product with superior quality	0.749	10.452	valid	
	Y22 <- Product with superior quality	0.871	15.183	valid	
	Y23 <- Product with superior quality	0.921	22.862	valid	
	Y31 <- Speed of service	0.861	7.128	valid	
	Y32 <- Speed of service	0.877	18.539	valid	
	Y33 <- Speed of service	0.913	8.539	valid	
Business Performance	Z11 <- Business Performance	0.796	11.076	valid	
	Z12 <- Business Performance	0.761	9.997	valid	

The result of measurement model of dimensions by its indicators show that the indicators are valid which the value of $t < 2.07$ (t table at $\alpha = 0.05$)

The result of measurement model of latent variables on their dimensions show to what extent the validity of dimensions in measuring latent variables. Following table show the result of measurement model for each latent variables on dimensions.

Table 3
Loading Factor of Latent Variable-Dimension

Latent Variable-Dimension	λ	t	conclusion
MARKET ATTRACTIVENESS -> Market forces	0.861	25.110	valid
MARKET ATTRACTIVENESS -> Competitive intensity	0.875	15.461	valid
MARKET ATTRACTIVENESS -> Market access	0.898	23.452	valid
DISTINCTIVE CAPABILITES -> Tangible asset	0.924	43.038	valid
DISTINCTIVE CAPABILITES ->>Intangible asset	0.961	91.704	valid
COMPETITIVENESS ->Speed of service	0.866	15.939	valid
COMPETITIVENESS ->Product with superior quality	0.799	11.292	valid
COMPETITIVENESS ->Competitive price	0.831	10.229	valid

The result of measurement model on dimensions show that all of dimensions are valid with the value of $t < 2.07$ (t table pada $\alpha = 0.05$)

Following figure show the complete path diagram:

Figure 1
Complete Path Diagram of Research Model

Hypotehsis testing

- The influence of market attractiveness and distinctive capabilities on competitiveness of the Hand Loom Industry in West Java**

Below is the result of hypothesis testing both simultaneous and partially.

a. Simultaneous Hypothesis testing

Below is the result of simultaneous testing of hypothesis 1:

Table 4
Simultaneous Testing of Hypothesis 1

Hypothesis	R ²	F	Conclusion
Market attractiveness and distinctive capabilities →Competitiveness	0.808	50,59*	Hypothesis accepted

* significant at $\alpha=0.05$ (F table =3.422)

Based on the table, it is known that within the degree of confidence of 95% ($\alpha=0.05$) simultaneously there is the influence of market attractiveness and distinctive capabilities on competitiveness amounted to 80.8%, while the rest of 19.2% is affected by other factor did not examined.

b. Partial Hypothesis testing

Below is the result of partial testing of hypothesis 1:

Table 5
Partial Testing of Hypothesis 1

Hypothesis	γ	t	R2	Conclusion
Market attractiveness→Competitiveness	0,473	3.367*	0.372	Hypothesis accepted
Distinctive capabilities →Competitiveness	0,537	4.179*	0.436	Hypothesis accepted

* significant at $\alpha=0.05$ (t table =2.03)

The table show that partially, distinctive capabilities and market attractiveness influential significantly to competitiveness, which is distinctive capabilities has a greater influence (43.6%).

2. The influence of market attractiveness and distinctive capabilities on business performance of the Hand Loom Industry in West Java

Below is the result of hypothesis testing both simultaneous and partially :

a. Simultaneous Hypothesis testing

Below is the result of simultaneous testing of hypothesis 2 :

Table 6
Simultaneous Testing of Hypothesis 2

Hypothesis	R ²	F	Conclusion
Market attractiveness and distinctive capabilities → Business Performance	0.143	12,01	Hypothesis rejected

* significant at $\alpha=0.05$ (F table =3.422)

According to the table test above is known that with the degree of confidence of 95% ($\alpha=0.05$), simultaneously there is not the influence of market attractiveness and distinctive capabilities on business performance, which the influence is only 14.3% while the rest of 85.7% is affected by other factor did not examined.

b. Partial Hypothesis testing

Below is the result of partial testing of hypothesis 2:

Table7
Partial Testing of Hypothesis 2

Hypothesis	γ	t	R ²	Conclusion
Market attractiveness → Business Performance	0.234	1.420	0.081	Hypothesis rejected
Distinctive capabilities → Business Performance	0.191	1.072	0.063	Hypothesis rejected

* significant at $\alpha=0.05$ (t table =2.03)

The table shows that partially both of market attractiveness and distinctive capabilities have not a significant influence on business performance, proven by the value of R² that very low.

3. The influence of competitiveness on business performance of the Hand Loom Industry in West Java

a. Partial Hypothesis testing

Below is the result of partial testing of hypothesis 3 :

Table 8
Partial Testing of Hypothesis 3

Hypothesis	β	t	R ²	Conclusion
COMPETITIVENESS - > BUSINESS PERFORMANCE	0.580	2.672*	0.336	Hypothesis accepted

* significant at $\alpha=0.05$ (t table =2.03)

The table shows that competitiveness is influential significantly to business performance as amounted to 33.6%.

Figure 2
Research Finding

Competitiveness is a dominant aspect in improving business performance directly. Competitiveness dominantly influenced by distinctive capabilities compared to market attractiveness. Then, it can be said that the improvement of business performance of Hand Loom Industry in West Java, influenced by competitiveness that formed by distinctive capabilities and adaptation of market attractiveness.

IV. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Distinctive capabilities and market attractiveness influential significantly on competitiveness which is distinctive capabilities has a greater influence, meanwhile both of them did not influential on business performance. The dominant aspect in improving business performance is competitiveness.

Competitiveness has a significant effect in improving business performance. To that end, the company’s management of non-machine suggested to prioritize the improvements in the products with superior quality, competitive pricing, and high levels of service delivery to the customer (speed and variety).

The development of the distinctive capabilities focused on the aspects of intangible assets and tangible assets, in terms of a more adequate facilities and infrastructure, the quality of raw material used, the development of the latest technology, current facilities production that able to fulfill orders effectively and efficiently, as well as the expansion of the factory area.

Market attractiveness should be adapted in the term of market access, competitive intensity, and market forces.

Suggested that findings of this study can be used as a reference for the next researcher to conduct a research related to the development Hand Loom by make these findings as part of the premise in preparing the framework.

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